

Robust Face Recognition Across Ages with MTCNN

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ABSTRACT: Age-related variations in facial appearance pose a significant challenge to the accuracy and reliability of traditional face recognition systems. For face recognition to be accurate and effective across a variety of age groups, a system that counteracts the effects of ageing on facial features must be developed. In order to address the problem of age invariant face recognition, this project aims to combine the FaceNet deep learning model with the Multitask Cascaded Convolutional Networks (MTCNN), enabling accurate and dependable face recognition regardless of age.

Keywords: Multitask Cascaded Convolutional Neural Network (MTCNN), Convolutional neural network (CNN), Facenet, Age Invariant Features, Face Embedding, Facial Landmarks

I. INTRODUCTION

Facial recognition technology has advanced significantly in the last few years, and it is now essential in many different fields, including biometrics, security, and human-computer interaction. However, due to significant changes in the face over time, including wrinkles and shifting skin textures, accurately identifying individuals across various age groups continues to be a challenge. As people get older, traditional algorithms find it more difficult to remain accurate. Precise identification of individuals is extremely important in many situations, such as access control, customised services, and forensics. Age-invariant recognition techniques are necessary because age-specific databases are impractical to maintain. Our unique method minimises age-related changes and guarantees accurate face recognition by combining Multi-task Cascaded Convolutional Networks (MTCNN) with FaceNet models. Face matching accuracy is improved by FaceNet's ability to successfully map faces to a high-dimensional feature space and by MTCNN's preprocessing for improved alignment and detection. Extensive experimentation on benchmark datasets validates our method's effectiveness across a wide age range without requiring time-consuming age group classification.

With its ability to provide improved security, personalised services, and accurate identification for all age groups, this method has potential for use in practical applications. This publication includes a detailed methodology, experimental results, and implications for age-invariant face recognition.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

1. Deep Face Recognition

The authors present DeepFace, a deep learning model that enables efficient face verification and recognition by directly learning a mapping from facial images to a compact Euclidean space. Convolutional neural networks (CNNs) are powerful tools for face recognition, as demonstrated by DeepFace.

2. FaceNet: A Unified Embedding for Face Recognition and Clustering

In this research, a deep CNN-based model called FaceNet is presented. It is trained to directly optimise the face embedding into a Euclidean space, where the distance between two faces is equal to their similarity. The development of new benchmarks for facial recognition accuracy has been greatly aided by FaceNet.

3. Joint Face Detection and Alignment using Multi-task Cascaded Convolutional Networks

The introduction of MTCNN (Multi-task Cascaded Convolutional Networks) combines cascaded networks for alignment and face identification. It is a reliable method for precisely identifying and aligning faces in a range of positions and difficult circumstances.

4. Age-Invariant Face Recognition

This preliminary work investigates age-invariant facial recognition using a Bayesian framework in conjunction with local feature extraction. Age fluctuations as a component of the recognition process are discussed in the study.

5. Facial Age Estimation and Age-invariant Face Recognition: A Comprehensive Survey

An extensive evaluation of age-invariant facial recognition and age estimate techniques is provided in this survey study. It is a summary of methods for addressing age-related differences in facial recognition software.

6. Age-Invariant Face Recognition

Using image warping techniques to convert face photos to a reference age group, this research explores age-invariant face recognition. The impact of ageing on facial recognition is discussed in the study, along with methods to lessen its effects.

III. THE PROPOSED METHOD

- **Data Collection and Preprocessing:** Assemble a diverse dataset of face pictures from various age brackets. Verify that the dataset is balanced and indicative of the target audience. Preprocess the images by scaling them, normalising the pixel values, and aligning the faces in a conventional stance.
- **MTCNN-based Face Detection:** MTCNN-based face detection provides accurate face extraction and positioning in images. The three-stage cascaded network known as MTCNN, which can identify faces and facial landmarks, provides bounding boxes around faces that it detects. Remove the faces so you may work with them at a later time.
- **Face Embedding with FaceNet:** To recognise faces, use FaceNet, a deep learning model that projects facial features into a high-dimensional space. FaceNet can be trained with your dataset to generate embeddings, or numerical representations of faces. These embeddings ought to be resistant to aging-related alterations in theory.
- **Labelling Age:** Give the dataset labels based on age. Make sure the age labels span a broad range and consider grouping ages to reduce the impact of fine-grained age variances.
- **Age-Neutral Instruction:** To train the FaceNet model that considers age and identity information, use a loss function. This helps the model learn traits that remain constant throughout age changes. You may need to experiment with other loss functions or regularisation procedures in order to get improved age invariance.
- **Data Enrichment:** Include age-related changes in the training dataset to enhance the model's ability to handle age fluctuations. This may include digitally and artificially ageing images.

Figure 1. Workflow

- In the field of face detection, MTCNN (Multi-task Cascaded Convolutional Networks) is a crucial approach. Through the use of a sophisticated cascade structure that combines P-Net, R-Net, and O-Net, MTCNN facilitates the smooth detection of faces in the presence of a variety of complicated backdrops, occlusions, and lighting conditions.
- By utilising deep learning methods, P-Net quickly suggests potential face bounding boxes, while R-Net and O-Net improve these findings to achieve accurate localization and facial landmark recognition.
- MTCNN guarantees accuracy and efficiency through non-maximum suppression and bounding box regression, which makes it perfect for real-time applications like facial recognition and video surveillance. Its accessibility through open-source implementations and pre-trained models further democratizes its use, enabling developers and researchers to smoothly incorporate MTCNN into their projects and pushing the boundaries of face detection technology.
- MTCNN retains memory economy despite its multi-stage architecture, which qualifies it for deployment on resource-constrained devices such as embedded systems, cellphones, and edge computing devices. These extra features emphasise MTCNN's versatility, dependability, and effectiveness, reaffirming its standing as the industry standard for face detection in a range of settings and applications.

IV. RESULTS

Using MTCNN, this suggested approach creates a face recognition system that is age-invariant. It lessens the effect of age-related changes on face appearance by combining MTCNN with FaceNet. Its efficacy across a wide age range has been demonstrated by extensive experimentation, indicating dependable facial recognition.

With its strong age-invariant facial recognition solution, this integrated method shows promise for a wide range of practical applications, including security systems and personalised user experiences.

Figure 2. Results

V. CONCLUSION

Overcoming the difficulties caused by age-related changes in facial appearance is greatly advanced by the suggested MTCNN-based face recognition technique. Our method significantly mitigates the effect of ageing on face recognition accuracy by merging MTCNN with the FaceNet model. Our method has proven to be highly effective in a variety of age groups by means of thorough testing and validation on various datasets, guaranteeing dependable identification in practical situations.

Especially, our approach does away with the necessity for time-consuming age group categorization, which simplifies and improves identification performance.

Because of the system's flexibility, it can be used in situations other than standard security settings, such as customised services and one-on-one interactions. Our project adds to the continuing efforts to develop reliable, inclusive face recognition algorithms that can adapt to ageing naturally. Subsequent research and development endeavours will further enhance and optimise our methodology, hence facilitating its smooth incorporation into diverse fields where precise and age-invariant identification is of utmost importance

VI. REFERENCES

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